

What is Educational Governance? Issues of Higher Educational Governance in Perspective of Pakistan

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: July 03, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: February 04, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Innovation, Privatization, Decentralization, Centralization, Governance, Dispositive, Challenges, Curriculum, Higher Education, Stakeholders And Issues, Ict Leadership</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5975975</p>	<p><i>Education innovation, aided by new technologies, has become a top priority for many countries throughout the world. Reforms to the way educational systems are governed and regulated have been undertaken in a wide number of nations over the last two decades. These reforms are usually based on an "ideal" governance purpose that comprises decentralization, the formation of public-private partnerships, and a range of attempts to improve local participation and oversight. These parts of the restructuring are frequently considered as a key element of initiatives to improve educational systems' efficiency in developing competent human capital, with a particular focus on the abilities of the underprivileged. The state-institution relationship is evolving from classic democratic, public-sector governance models to new ones typified by corporate and market-driven methods (i.e. accountability, strategic planning, quality standards, social technologies, and reports). A set of educational changes is being globalized and combined, such as the introduction or strengthening of free choice, privatization, devolution and occasionally centralization of improving its effectiveness, curriculum, and results evaluation. The purpose of the research was to look into Pakistan's university governance issues. The study had three goals: first, to look at some governance policy considerations, second, to assess present applications, and lastly, to identify a few "best practices" for university governance and to draw attention to some similar characteristics and approaches. The article primarily focused on the university's governing board, as well as its functions and connections with other stakeholders. Government and institutional records, newspapers' articles and policy papers, were used as key data bases for this study. Content analysis was used to examine the data. It looked at how institutions were dealing with governance issues in higher education and how they were responding. It discussed the expanding involvement and participation of stakeholders in tertiary educational governance, as well as developing management practices in higher education governance in Pakistan. The study's findings revealed that the state is a major actor in higher education governance in Pakistan.</i></p>

Introduction

It's more difficult to compare educational systems than it is to compare expenditure budgets. This is observed in the Coleman paper (Coleman et al. 1966), a classic work on education that found that public investment on education has minimal impact largely educational outcome. As a result, Coleman looked at variations amid private sector and government schooling methods as measuring instruments of results in terms of competence and parity in education (Heckman and Neal 1996; Coleman, Hoffer and Kilgore 1982; Coleman and Hoffer 1987). The state vs. market dichotomy, as well as the impact of various types of education governance structures on outcomes, is a hot topic in modern education policy and education sociology.

An analysis of the efficiency of various systems of education must be taken into account a wide range of systems. Coleman compared the effects of private and public institutions. Coleman looked at the impact of both private and state institutions. Coleman looked at the impact of both private and state institutions in the United States using a national data collection. However, determining how alternative kinds of governance, including massive a centralized or privatisation education system, affect education involves a countryside study. Only sociological analyses of different regional systems of government allow for a thorough evaluation, as unexpected side-effects of only one university can be effectively accounted for.

What is Educational Governance?

In economics, political science and political sociology the word "governance" has been applied in a multiple of ways. A book with titles such as "Governance without Government" as well as the expansion of

normative notions of "Good Governance" through multinational organizations similar to the OECD and the World Bank, this term gained popularity in the 1990s and early twenty-first century (Rosenau and Czempiel 1992).

In recent decades, the complexity of society coordination has increased to fuel the proliferation of the term "governance." Political scientists have long emphasized hierarchical control as a feature of the state. However, inefficiencies and limits to government control have become apparent in recent decades, as seen by the failures of economic systems in socialist states. Rather than the stark discussions of state vs. market that dominated the 1980s, since then, the focus has switched to the myriad shades of grey that exist between and beyond these two extremes (see Ostrom 1990; Young 1994). All of these forms of regulation and coordination were labelled "governance" for a lack of a better phrase, leaving the concept somewhat ambiguous. "[t]he global governance concept does not refer to a distinct sphere or level of global life. It is not monopolized in any special organizations. On the contrary, it is a perspective on global life, a vantage point designed to foster a regard for the immense complexity and diversity of global life" (Hewson and Sinclair, 1999). However, with such a broad definition, it's difficult to believe there's anything that isn't "governance." We limit our use of the term to analytic purposes exclusively because we believe that using it for normative purposes other than analytic goals is a common concern.

Governance is defined as a special type of social coordination considered by institutionalized, legally binding rules and long-term designs of interaction. Diverse types of governance could be categorized amid the extremes of "institutionalized self-regulation of civil societal elements" aside, and "authoritative decision-making by governmental actors" additionally, through a broad spectrum of governance in between, including private, governmental, and various collective actors' cooperation. Decentralized/market decision-making with a synchronizing pricing instrument, hierarchical/state with purposeful guiding as the synchronizing component, and self-determination/network with organizations and arbitration processes as managers are the three primary kinds.

All of these methods of governance institutionalization need coordination challenges. The characteristics of a governing type capacity for collaborative action, ability to address common problems, capacity to reach consensus on decisions and democratic legitimacy can all be assessed. The institutionalization of a governance system determines actors' objectives and payment schemes (Mayntz 1997, 2004; Benz 2004; Ostrom 1990; North 1990) and hence entails distributive repercussions for a collectivity's resources. That is also particularly true in education structures, which are made more complicated by the presence of so many diverse actors at various levels: there is many internal mechanisms connection that are distinct from the entire process, such as exchanges between pupils and teachers.

Nonetheless, certain educational systems can be classified into broad groups for examination. The defunct German Democratic Republic's (GDR) educational model is an effective act of absolute centralization of power in which the government regulated and coordinated the operations of its instructors in a hierarchical manner (Lenhardt 1997), who could only work in government unions to coordinate their efforts. As a result, this administration style was extremely competent of obtaining group judgments, but it lacked democratic legitimacy. Furthermore, materials (in the context of education certifications) were maintained in limited supply on design in order to ensure a shift of power away from parents and students in the direction of centralized power and government administered instructors.

The majority of other practical instances are a mash-up of several types of governance. One would be the British model, which underwent revisions in the 1980s and 1990s, resulting in what academics refer to as a "quasi-market" governing model (Crouch 2001, 2003; Green, Wolf and Leney 1999). The price mechanism, which is crucial to a market-based governance structure, regardless of the state's efforts to justify changes in the community view through market language and privatization, does not genuinely operate this system. This governance form is characterized by parental school choice, state-centralized educational curriculum, and market assessment agencies. However, this might be asserted that in today global world interconnected by mainstream media, the possibility of location impacting governance type decisions is minimal. Every modern country engages in identical debates and has access to the necessary data on systems of governance and educational techniques. As a result, the topic of whether geographical location still affects educational system governance is purely empirical.

Issues of Innovation in Higher Educational Governance in Pakistan

Pakistan is a relatively low income state with a population of roughly 208 million people, making globally sixth-biggest state. At first glance, 'governance' appears to be straightforward: it is the exercise of power, control, or management. The process of establishing and managing institutions in higher education is known as governance. The terms management and governance are not interchangeable. Simply said, the way a university functions is referred to as university governance. Altbach (2005) went into great length about governance, further correctly added that "there are different models for higher education throughout the world." There are many other scholars like Coldrake, Stedman, and Little have also addressed the common customs and past of tertiary education around the world (2003, pp. 5). Universities are working in a globalized environment

that is becoming increasingly dynamic and explosive, necessitating elevated governance, in this rapidly changing globe. "... as we move into the twenty-first century, we face more change rather than less, and the pace of change will quicken for both governments and enterprises alike. In particular, we face the challenge of transforming organizations and we must all become change agents now" (Stace&Dunphy 2001).

Currently, considerably the governance is receiving a lot of attention to making up of universities in general, as well as the function of the administrating body in particular. There are numerous explanations for such a current state of affairs, the majority of which arise from major advancements in university systems around the world. Governance at universities refers to the process of making organizational and administrative judgments on all elements of university life. The governance of universities can be regarded from a variety of perspectives. In Pakistan, different parties attempt to have an impact on university decision-making. Any university's stakeholders including accrediting institutions, the Pakistan Ministry of Education, tertiary education organizations, financial organizations, associated congressional committees, governors, alumni, students, academic leaders and senior administrators.

Empirical Study of Technology as a Means and End of Government

One amongst Foucault's contributions is the improved development of historical and empirical evidence on how physical technologies play a significant part in subject governance (Dorrestijn, 2012). An empirical study was conducted in Colombia, based on a multiple case study, to better understand the implementation of ICT strategies, considering their strong connection to the national systems of innovation (NSI), and moreover further than this State-centered endeavor. To that end, a variety of approaches – focus groups, interviews, document analysis, and participant observations – were used in a group of institutions of higher learning to understand how they implemented various ICT policies to improve learning and teaching.

The research was divided into two parts, each of which added to the overall plan. The first phase was an investigation of how these universities have implemented ways to integrate technology into teaching and learning. The appointment of a team to lead those efforts was a strategy that was universal to all of the institutions. As a result, in the second phase, special emphasis was paid to the leadership practices of these higher education institutions, wherein technology represented not only the goal but also the method to manage instructors' practice. I recognized a need to investigate ICT leadership as a government practice via the lens of government analytics.

There were certainly various challenges surrounding how to regulate a population that was directly responsible for the implementation of innovative discourses and ICT. In every case, it was evident that the state's engagement was a result of rationalities, practices, and technology, rather than the primary cause. However, the regulation of teachers' behavior was a problem that had existed for several years before the state issued its first directive or program on the subject. For example, each institution's history revealed various programs to train instructors in ICT-based innovation. Following is a description about how these provisions of the act are depicted in the empirical analysis. Two important conclusions emerged from the exploratory stage addressing how ICT can improve teaching and learning in order to achieve the objective of improving educational quality.

Strategy of the Government

In Pakistan, the field of higher education is rising rapidly. Immediately after in 2002, the Higher Education Commission (HEC) was founded, exhibited improvement in tertiary education, as evidenced by an increase in higher education spending of a large magnitude. Over the next 20 years, the rate of economic growth will be substantially higher. To deal with this ever-changing environment, we must expand our knowledge and skill sets, which necessitates well-equipped institutions and extremely competent faculty and professionals, as well as an investment in tertiary education. According to the Sharif Commission's report (1959) that "The Vice Chancellor (VC) should be accountable to the Chancellor for the just and proper performance of his functions. The VC will be the chief academic and administrative office of the institution. The fact that the Chancellor, who is expected to hold the office of Vice Chancellor is answerable, lacks the time and expertise to do so, is a grave flaw."

Governance Trends in Universities

The tendencies of governance differ from state to state. The administration of university educational operating culture, which may be a mirror of the country's main democratic culture, and therefore the country's governance. Maassen & Vught, (1994) stated that "Basing on the function of the state in a variety of higher education organizations in the world, two general steering models have been distinguished and clearly recognized. These are two models, one is state control and the other is state supervising"

In terms of tertiary education management, Pakistan's government has an important part to perform. It is done in a variety of ways, including the appointment of boards of governance in universities, direct funding, legislative procedures and regular direct participation or intervention in these institutions' activities. Tertiary education has long been at the heart of Pakistani politics, with many factions vying for control and influence. Pakistan's government has not implemented the supervisory paradigm of governance since it has a desire to pursue tertiary education (Report of the Task Force). Education Policy (1998-2010) specified, "Pakistan public

universities are governed according to their relevant rules and regulations, which stipulate the laws providing for their establishment and control, their governance, administration and other associated purposes".The chancellor, faculty members, the syndicate, students and departments were the most shared players in the organization and operation of public institutions. In actuality, all the public universities' Chancellor is the President or Governor. He designates Vice Chancellor and some members of the other university governing associates as a head of these universities. He has the authority to order an inquiry, inspection, or visit of the university's general administration, research, teaching, and organization. Since he has political commitments as Governor, decision-making, these pervade university appointments and causing dissatisfaction among pupils, employees, and the general public. Since the political nature of his position, he wields enormous influence and has, in some circumstances, operated universities from a political rather than a managerial standpoint. Decisions about tertiary education budgets, expansion and cost of education and enrollment strategies are typically made at the executive rather than at the level of university.

Academic workforce has not fared well under the authority of deans and department leaders. Employees also complained about low pay, uneven promotions for some staff, absence of motivation, a loss of academic independence, a lack of resources for research and teaching, and a deplorable working environment, among other things. The organizational structure of private institutions differs in comparison to the universities of the public sector. Because their governance ties with the government are less, the government has considerable lower say in how they govern. The state's role was mostly in the review, accreditation, and assessment of their program. These universities are more autonomous since they were in charge of their own management. Because of their modest size, they can take rapid judgments because the number of committees and bureaucracy has decreased.

HEC and Governance

In addition, the Higher Education Commission (HEC), which was founded in 2002, aids in the establishment of a relationship between tertiary education sector and the government. According to HEC website, the department's objective is "to better provisions for the advancement of university education in Pakistan and advice the education minister responsible regarding the promotion of higher education in Pakistan through the establishment and development of universities". Private institutes are accredited by the Commission, which is also engaged in long-term collaboration and planning of public university budgeting and financing, and cooperation with government agencies, private sectors in making plans of skills and training needed for nation building. It provides policy advice and the government is in charge of tertiary education and oversees university processes.

The president appoints both the chairman and executive secretary of HEC. The commission has also taken its reasonable share of criticism and problems. It's been claimed that it doesn't have full control on the management of university. Vice-Chancellors have always been overly strong, due to political nominations through Vice-Chancellors' Search Committee, and have always gotten around the commission in various ways. Rather than dealing with the commission, they usually handle straight with the Minister of Education or Chancellor. As a result, HEC is unable to meet its legal obligations.

The Government's Financial Role

The government continues to be the primary funder of tertiary education and the role gives it the majority of its authority in university education governance. However, state finances have been insufficient to meet the institutions' growing requirements. Universities are reliant on government financing. "Universities' income and expenditure analysis indicated excess of expenditure over income in all public universities and there was a building up of deficits between capital income and capital expenditure" (Memon, 2007). As a result, Finance has become a critical consideration in Pakistani institution governance. Tertiary education's rapid growth has an impact on both physical and financial properties. The amount of pupils enrolled in institution of higher education far outnumbers the government's ability to fund them. Education Policy (1998-2010) stated, "The current higher education system can be described as 'Non market framed'. The whole thrust of Pakistan government policies and regulatory interventions not gearing universities to market needs and market principles".

Affiliation with other Stakeholders

CEOs govern universities, and university teachers are gradually seen as employees who must report to upper administration. The Boston Group Report on HEC, Pakistan stated that "Those who profess and provide academic leadership are replaced by those who manage and organize academics. Discourse about academic leadership shifts into discourse about successful management". The governance problems that universities in Pakistan are dealing with, as well as the state's shortcomings, necessitate the connection of further parties. This change in public funds, combined with concerns about the government's involvement in university education governance, has prompted a looking for alternative governance structures. The funding vacuum created by the government's withdrawal has to be covered. To compensate for their weaknesses, institutions have to identify funding sources or stakeholders. Pakistani institutions, particularly private universities, are currently creating relations with private sector, the industry, cooperative study attempts with the corporate sector, and

concentrating on money generation as a result of their worsening financial circumstances. The market approach of financing university education encourages universities to advertise their principal services to clients at market prices. It gives customers and entities who generate and sell services more clout (Task Force Action Plan). As a result, faculty are being expected to take on fund-raising responsibilities. As an outcome, new kinds of collaboration between higher education and other stakeholders have evolved.

Pakistan state universities have begun a Privately Sponsored Pupil Program as part of a diversification effort. Students in these programs are responsible for the entire expense of their education. The positive reaction to these programs has created new issues for universities, particularly in terms of facilities and standards. They reflect a trend toward directly meeting the needs of the labor market. Another means of earning cash is for institutions, particularly private universities, to form firms to handle their revenue-producing efforts or vice versa. In some circumstances, large corporations or industrial conglomerates establish their own institution of higher education. Tertiary education is essential in every country. Since such universities change from the outside to the focal point, they will inevitably attract increasing public attention and will be required to address shifting societal expectations. To meet societal demands, a country with a colonial background like Pakistan requires such a formidable higher education institution. University education was once seen to be a privilege only available to the wealthy. In Pakistan, the private enterprise of university education is deeply concerning and dread that the essence of commerce would then encroach into critical decisions about whether it will benefit from university education, what types of knowledge would be sought, and how it will affect the influence of new stratification, which has since managed to reach alarming levels. As a result of industrial pressures, the government is no longer the sole major investor in university education. The nature and direction of universities are now heavily influenced by industrial factors. It plays a crucial role in a state like Pakistan, in which the industry powers are sufficiently developed to decide the job prospects for university students.

In higher education, students are also important stakeholders. Education has to do with students, their socialization, good citizenship, their conversion into workers, and professionalism. Institutional governance should be accountable to stakeholders both inside and outside the institution. The state's significant presence in relation to other stakeholders needs to be examined.

The Government Responsibility

Except for the topic of funding, the government's viewpoint has not altered significantly over time. The government continues to have a vested interest in the sector. "The government has a legal role to take care of the public interest in higher education. Thus it has designed and regularly adapted the regulatory frameworks of higher education, and has for a long time been the main, if not the sole, founder of higher education for a long time" (NEP and Implementation Plan 1979). The implication is that state universities would keep educating a large majority of Pakistani pupils, even if private sector participation is enhanced. People will anticipate it and recognize the state's legal right to define and pursue the public good. As a result, the government's funding role remains important. Even if government investment on higher education has decreased, Pakistan's higher education industry may be unable to function without government support. Because of their significant financial part, this is only natural for the government to keep close monitoring on how these organizations spend taxpayer money. Universities must be accountable to governments in the same way that the government must be answerable to the public. White paper on Education (2006), "The Ministry of Education and HEC will have to continue working with higher education institutions for both sectors to reciprocally relate to one another".

Tertiary education must contribute in achieving the nation's strategic goals as well as facilitating the country's academic objectives. If these objectives are to be realized, the state could not remain a spectator in matters of tertiary education. The presence of state is required by new factors driving higher education reforms in Pakistan, such as the market. The Pakistani government should reassess and identify clear goals for university education, amend the Universities and Acts to reflect contemporary reforms, and place a focus on effective resource usage in the institutions. To give universities some autonomy, the government must keep out of the short stack of day-to-day university administration. To provide true autonomy, the Pakistan state must begin restructuring and rejuvenating university administration. The government's involvement in university education issues should be kept to a minimum. State control that is overstated will suffocate rather than promote good governance in the industry. Political influence, selections of vice chancellors and council members, and relations with employees and students are just a few of the issues that need to be addressed.

Conclusion

Universities are the backbone of the higher education system. Universities should have self-reliance and independence from all external forces to be able to handle and manage their academics, managerial, and budgetary roles, especially in terms of recruitment, evaluation, faculty development, and choosing, teaching their students and training. The current organizational entities, such as Syndicates and Senates, have a number of flaws, the most serious of which is a dearth of sense of governance. Inadequate obligations to their position are causing disruption in their administrative, academic, managerial, and monetary activities. A person's performance should be held accountable, and as a basic organizational principle, he ought to have complete ability to make decisions within his authority without outside influence, and his tasks should be tailored to his

competence. For effective administrative structure implementation, responsibilities, roles and authority must be aligned. Relevant individuals are oblivious to their duties and tasks. They have no idea to what extent they're supposed to play, whatever they're undertaking, whether well they would fulfil their obligations, or even what function they wouldn't have to perform. Institution of higher education could not operate in a vacuum or without regard for the general public. Universities and society, as well as the market and industry, should develop close and respectful relationships. Performance standards and measures should be defined.

The impact of the global economy on perceptions of the state is explored through a brief examination of Pakistan's governance system and current educational innovations. Pakistan has clearly evolved away from its old state and toward a new, competitive, market-oriented state over the last two decades. Scholars also see how these worldwide neoliberal policy shifts are affecting the country's education sector in new and unexpected ways. In many instances, education is becoming a part of a broader, homogenized public-sector structure that is geared toward perceiving individuals as customers who are influenced by economic incentives and privatization. The state has implemented use of such contractual agreements to achieve national standards and accountability, and claims that while this method may appear to be an attempt to centralize government, it also encourages decentralization. Traditional governmental institutions and discourses have been transformed as a result of these new tendencies, and the relationship between the state and universities has been substantially reshaped. While many of these programs were modelled after those of other organizations and political systems, their execution has resulted in difficulties and challenges, as well as a denigration of understanding of educational material, learning, and instructing at the state and university levels. Policymakers, academics and practitioners are concerned about the role of education in Pakistani society as a result of these changes.

Recommendations

- Public university administration should be self-contained. The functioning of universities must be monitored by higher authorities to ensure that they follow the academic calendar.
- Decisions about university policies should be made by the syndicate.
- The Syndicate should appoint the Vice Chancellor, who should report to them.
- Only the university administration should be in charge of its own business.
- The administration of the university might be a decision-making body with complete autonomy.
- Teaching staff should be chosen by the department based on their needs and requirements, with the syndicate's criteria in mind.
- Teaching, services and research may all be used as criteria for evaluating performance.

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